

Charismatic Renewal Movement in Christianity - Second Wave Pentecostalism

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Christian Traditions, Catholic, 'Roman' Catholic, Pentecostal, Evangelical (charismatic), Protestantism

For the first six decades of the 20th Century, Pentecostalism was viewed with skepticism and often outright dismissed by other denominations of Christianity. Many Christians believed Pentecostals to be chaotic and disorderly. Pentecostal practices of speaking in tongues, their beliefs in divine healing and prophecy, and their unorganized and noisy prayer gatherings ostracized them from other established Protestant traditions believed to be more orderly and respectable. They were seen as a fringe group that stood outside of the traditions of mainline and evangelical branches of the larger Protestant community. However, Pentecostalism and a majority of the Christian communities in the United States would undergo a massive shift as Pentecostal theology and practices burst into the “orderly” worlds of mainline denominations and swept across denominational boundaries beginning in 1960. In a small Episcopalian parish in Van Nuys, CA in April 1960, the charismatic renewal found its genesis when Reverend Dennis Bennett shared his experience of being baptized in the Spirit and speaking in tongues. His announcement angered his congregation and he was asked to resign shortly after sharing his experiences. Despite the parishioners of St. Mark’s Episcopal Church being told to not speak about what Reverend Bennett shared about, one parishioner was not going to be quiet. Jean Stone was a parishioner who began a media campaign to chronicle and share about Reverend Bennett’s experience. Stone got Time Magazine and Newsweek to write articles about the renewal movement and Bennett became the defacto face of the Charismatic Renewal movement in the United States. As Bennett’s story spread throughout the country, other clergy from mainline Protestant denominations began to share about their experiences of being baptized in the Holy Spirit. Methodists, Lutherans, Baptists, Presbyterians, Anglicans, Mennonites, Roman Catholics, and others began to open up about their Pentecostal experience and many began to practice speaking in tongues, prophesying, healing, and deliverance. Although there is an overlap between some of the beliefs between Pentecostals and Charismatics, there are some key differences. Both groups believe in the Baptism of the Holy Spirit, which is an experience that often takes place after conversion (although some adherents experience the Baptism of the Holy Spirit at their conversion). A key difference is the evidence of being baptized in the Holy Spirit. Pentecostals believe that a person must speak in tongues in order to demonstrate that they have been baptized in the Spirit. Charismatics claim that although many people do speak in tongues as their first sign, it is not the only sign that accompanies being baptized in the Holy Spirit. Any manifestations of the gifts of the Holy Spirit outlined in the New Testament are recognized by Charismatics as being baptized in the Spirit. The Charismatic Renewal Movement validated Historical Pentecostal churches and movements as part of the American Christian landscape. Prior to the movement, Mainline and Protestant denominations viewed Pentecostalism with disdain and were weary of their theology and practices. However, the media coverage of Reverend Dennis Bennett’s experiences in California in 1960, as well as the rise in denominational clergy sharing about their own experiences of being baptized in the Holy Spirit, led mainline denominational leaders to address the Charismatic renewal movements taking place in their churches. Most of these denominations ultimately accepted Charismatic adherents as part of their tradition. Other denominations left their position on the charismatic renewal movement open without rejecting the movement outright.

Date Range: 1960 CE - 2020 CE

Region: USA

Region tags: United States, Lower 48, United States of America, North America

The United States of America

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Synan, Vinson. *The Holiness-Pentecostal Tradition*. Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1997.
- Source 1: Bowler, Kate. *Blessed: A History of the American Prosperity Gospel*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2013.
- Source 1: Eskridge, Larry. *God's Forever Family: The Jesus People Movement in America*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2013.
- Source 1: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology: Systematic Theology from a Charismatic Perspective*. Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 1996.
- Source 1: Synan, Vinson. *The Century of the Holy Spirit*. Nashville: Thomas Nelson, Inc., 2001.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=o28Lc-m6xoE>
- Source 1 Description: Footage from the 1977 Charismatic Renewal Conference at Arrowhead Stadium in Kansas City, MO.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-XE6tOVWTGU&list=PLodjFYFcE0XJCQBOUEQKevTFg5vsb7>
- Source 1 Description: Video compilation of Rev. Dennis Bennett recounting his experience of being Baptized in the Holy Spirit.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3D2WhjcvXUA>
- Source 1 Description: Video from Christian Broadcasting Network celebrating the history of the Roman Catholic Charismatic Renewal movement that started in 1967.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yAUaftNbR00>
- Source 1 Description: Archbishop of Canterbury, Justin Welby, shares about praying in tongues and other Charismatic practices.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9PHmrj80yrk>
- Source 1 Description: Pastor Harald Bredesen, an early leader in the Charismatic Renewal movement, preaches on how to receive the Baptism of the Holy Spirit.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=U2UjIhwt9d8>
- Source 1 Description: Lonnie Frisbee shares his experience of being Baptized by the Holy Ghost on the

Kathryn Kuhlman Show.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://aldersgaterenewal.org/guidelines-umc>

– Source 1 Description: United Methodist Guidelines regarding charismatic practices

– Source 1 URL: https://www.episcopalarchives.org/sites/default/files/publications/1964_GC_Journal.pdf

– Source 1 Description: The Journal of the General Convention published in 1964 provides a study of Episcopal bishops who responded to the rise of the Charismatic renewal taking place in their churches and declared that God was moving in new ways.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Charismatic Renewal Movement was all about different Christian traditions being in contact with one another. For the first six decades of the 20th century, Pentecostalism was viewed as a fringe or unorthodox movement amongst mainline and evangelical Christian denominations in the United States. However, numerous clergy from established Protestant denominations were experiencing the Baptism of the Holy Spirit and speaking in tongues during the first half of the century. Despite the increase in experiences amongst mainline denominational leaders, there was not one coherent meta-movement that joined them together until 1960. In April 1960, Reverend Dennis Bennett of St. Mark's Episcopal Church in Van Nuys, CA shared his experience of being Baptized in the Holy Spirit and speaking in tongues. His congregation revolted and forced him to resign as the minister of the church. However, one parishoner named Jean Stone supported Rev. Bennett and believed his experience needed to be shared beyond the walls of St. Mark's Episcopal Church. Stone got Newsweek and Time Magazine to publish articles about Rev. Bennett's experience. This media push led to Rev. Bennett becoming the face of the Charismatic Renewal Movement in the United States. The movement also became the meta-category for other mainline and evangelical leaders to describe their experiences of being baptized in the Holy Spirit and speaking in tongues. During the 1960s, leaders from numerous denominations such as Lutheran Church - Missouri Synod, United Methodist, Presbyterian, Southern Baptists, Episcopal, Anglican, and Mennonite came out and shared about their experiences of being Baptized in the Holy Spirit and speaking in tongues or experiencing physical healing. The revelation of these experiences led denominations to address charismatic phenomena in their congregations as well as how to reconcile their theology and practices with Pentecostal theology and practices. The Charismatic Renewal Movement also came into contact with the Roman Catholic Church in the United States. The Roman Catholic Charismatic Movement began in 1967 at at Duquesne University in Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania. Ralph Kiefer, a graduate student, and William Storey, a professor, both from Duquesne University attended an Episcopal prayer gathering and were baptized in the Holy Spirit. They returned to campus and started praying for faculty and students who were subsequently baptized in the Spirit. Similar experiences at the University of Notre Dame began to take place. As a result, the Roman Catholic Church began to address the charismatic phenomenon throughout the country and ultimately led to Pope Paul VI officially embracing charismatic Catholics in 1975.

Reference: Synan, Vinson. *The Century of the Holy Spirit*. Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson, 2000.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Pastor John MacArthur in Los Angeles, CA continues to be a particularly fierce critic of Pentecostalism and the Charismatic Renewal Movement. Pastor MacArthur hosted a conference called Strange Fire where he and other evangelical leaders critiqued the validity of the modern Charismatic movement. The Strange Fire Conference from 2013 on youtube - <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLcpTMSL-FR-duxHk-xYVLOGCQRLnYBNxU>. There is still contention from cessationists about the legitimacy of Charismatic experiences. Other pastoral leaders and academics responded to the Strange Fire Conference to refute their analysis and teachings. A notable rebuttal came from Michael Brown, Ph.D. Dr. Brown is a professor and radio host of his show, In the Line of Fire. He wrote the book, Authentic Fire, in response to Pastor MacArthur's conference. These recent clashes between MacArthur and Pentecostal/Charismatic leaders is not new. J. Rodman Williams also engaged with MacArthur at the turn of the 21st Century. Williams shared, "In his book Charismatic Chaos, John F. MacArthur, Jr. frequently stresses the priority of biblical truth over experience. For example, "Experience, however, is not the test of biblical truth; rather, biblical truth stands in final judgment on experience." MacArthur writes these words in connection with his charge that charismatics give priority to experience over Scripture. As one against whom MacArthur levels this charge, I should like to make reply. I have no disagreement with MacArthur about the priority of biblical truth or theology over experience, but I am concerned primarily about the way MacArthur handles biblical truth in regard to the charismatic renewal." Charismatic Renewalists like Williams do not disagree with the authority of the Bible. The disagreement lies with the experience that a person has in regard to the Baptism of the Holy Spirit. This disagreement is very important between Pentecostal/Charismatic traditions and Evangelical traditions that are not part of the Charismatic movement. Many Evangelicals identify as cessationists, which means that they believe the spiritual gifts of tongues, prophecy, and healing ceased after the first apostles died. These gifts were for the birth of the church but not for practice beyond the establishment of the church.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: Pentecostal theology embraces the belief that there is an experience that practitioners can experience after salvation called the Baptism of the Holy Spirit. The Baptism of the Holy Spirit is based on the narrative of Acts 2 where the followers of Jesus received the Holy Spirit and spoke in tongues. Those who were baptized in the Spirit were empowered to minister as Jesus did in the gospel accounts and were able to perform supernatural feats such as healing and prophecy. To be identified as a Pentecostal or Charismatic, a practitioner needs to have evidence that they have been baptized in the Holy Spirit. Traditional Pentecostals declare that a person must speak in tongues as evidence. Charismatics in the second wave usually state that any manifestation of the gifts of the Holy Spirit is evidence of a person's baptism in the Spirit. In both cases, practitioners are invited to receive the Baptism of the Holy Spirit through prayer. It is common for a leader or layperson to lay hands on those wishing to receive the baptism and to pray for the person to experience the Spirit in a new way. The person receiving prayer is also invited to pray and to ask for the baptism. Often people who are baptized in the Spirit exhibit physical manifestations of trembling and speaking in tongues. There are two forms of speaking in tongues within the Pentecostal and Charismatic traditions. The first is called xenoglossy where a person speaks a known spoken language that they have never learned before. A Lutheran leader named Harald Bredesen shared about his experience of xenoglossy. He was in prayer seeking God for the baptism of the Spirit and explained, "I tried to say, 'Thank You, Jesus, thank You, Jesus,' but I couldn't express the inexpressible. Then, to my great relief, the Holy Spirit did it for me. It was just as if a bottle was uncorked, and out of me poured a torrent of words in a language I had never studied before." Bredesen started to walk around and he ran into a girl who heard him speaking and told him, "You're speaking Polish." With this information, the young girl took Bredesen to find a local Polish man who could confirm his language. The girl led him to a man who heard Bredesen speak and exclaimed, "Bracia, Bracia! You called me Brother... You are praising God, going from one Slavic dialect to another." The second is called glossolalia, which is where a person speaks an unintelligible language, often referred to as a heavenly or angelic language. Professor J. Rodman Williams recalled, "Instead of articulating rational words I began to ejaculate sounds of any kind, praying that somehow the Lord would use them. Suddenly I realized that something drastic was happening: my noises were being left

behind, and I was off with such utterance, such words as I had never heard before."

Reference: Synan, Vinson. *The Century of the Holy Spirit*. Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson, 2000.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. "A Theological Pilgrimage". Christian Broadcasting Network, n.d..
https://www.cbn.com/spirituallife/biblestudyandtheology/drwilliams/bk_theopilgrim.aspx?mobile=false&u=1.

Reference: Bredesen, Harald, and Pat King. *Yes, Lord!*. Baker Books, 2008.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=qG6JBAAAQBAJ>.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: The Baptism of the Holy Spirit is an experience that takes place subsequent to conversion (although sometimes the baptism of the Holy Spirit takes place at conversion for some people). The practitioner is often encouraged by a pastor or leader to seek the Baptism of the Spirit. It must be sought after and is usually not a random experience. J. Rodman Williams, an early Charismatic Renewal theologian, wrote about his experience that reflects many other experiences of those seeking the Baptism of the Holy Spirit. "I felt at ease, and began to turn to letters on my desk. One letter was from a pastor who described his experience of recently visiting the seminary and being prayed for by a student to receive the gift of the Holy Spirit. He wrote about how later he began to speak in tongues and praise God mightily. As I read and re-read the letter, the words somehow seemed to leap off the page, and I found myself being overcome. I was soon on my knees practically in tears praying for the Holy Spirit, and pounding the chair - asking, seeking, knocking - in a way I never had done before. Now I intensely yearned for the gift of the Holy Spirit. Then I stood and began to beseech God to break me open, to fill me to the fullest--with sometimes an almost torturous cry to what was in myself to possess my total being."

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. "A Theological Pilgrimage". The Christian Broadcasting Network, n.d..

https://www.cbn.com/spirituallife/biblestudyandtheology/drwilliams/bk_theopilgrim_preface.aspx?mobile=false&u=1.

Reference: Synan, Vinson. *The Century of the Holy Spirit*. Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson, 2000.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: The Baptism of the Holy Spirit is done through prayer and often times is accompanied by the practice of fasting. A person who wants to be baptized in the Holy Spirit may pray privately but it is often done with clergy or other laypersons who pray for the person seeking experience. A unique aspect of the Charismatic Renewal Movement was the surprise that accompanied many of the early leaders who received the Baptism of the Holy Spirit. Rev. Dennis Bennett explained, "I suppose I must have prayed out loud for about twenty minutes - at least it seemed to be a long time - and was just about to give up when a very strange thing happened. My tongue tripped, just as it might when you are trying to recite a tongue twister, and I began to speak a new language! Right away I recognized several things: first, it wasn't some kind of psychological trick or compulsion. There was nothing compulsive about it... Secondly, it was a real language, not some kind of 'baby talk.' It had grammar and syntax; it had inflection and expression - and it was beautiful."

Reference: Bennett, Dennis. *Nine O'clock in the Morning*. Alachua, FL: Bridge Logos, 1970.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Although many adherents engage in proselytization of non-Christians, many Charismatics proselytize within their denominations in regards to the Baptism of the Holy Spirit. There is a belief that Christians who are not Baptized in the Spirit are missing out on experiencing the power of God in their lives. Those who are baptized in the Spirit are doing ministry the way Jesus did in the Gospel accounts in the New Testament. Charismatics often share with non-Charismatics about their experience of being baptized in the Spirit. In addition, they often invite people to experience the baptism of the Spirit. Sometimes this happens in one-on-one interaction and other times the invitation is given at large gatherings.

Reference: Synan, Vinson. *The Holiness-pentecostal Tradition*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing, 1997.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=Q-npoRWoZuUC>.

Reference: Menzies, William, and Robert Menzies. *Spirit and Power: Foundations of Pentecostal Experience*. Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2000.

Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: At the end of the gospel of Matthew, Jesus Christ declares that followers of him are to make disciples and baptize them in the name of the Father, Son, and Holy Spirit. Most pastors who were or are part of Charismatic Renewal Movement take this command seriously and believe it is their responsibility as well as the responsibility of others to direct people to the person and work of Jesus Christ.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Followers of Jesus are mandated to make disciples and baptize them in the name of the Father, Son, and Holy Spirit (Matthew 28:19). However, most participants in the Charismatic Renewal believe this statement but it is not a requirement to be a Charismatic.

Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Some Charismatic traditions believe in Arminian theology and thus believe that a person who is saved can lose their salvation. Charismatic traditions that are rooted in Calvinistic and Reformed traditions may disagree with the Arminian position and adhere to their belief that those who are elected to salvation cannot lose it.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 21272000

Notes: Johnson, T.M. The Global Demographics of the Pentecostal and Charismatic Renewal. Soc 46, 479-483 (2009). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12115-009-9255-0>

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 14.5

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Protestant Charismatics use the Protestant Bible as their source of Scripture. Adherents from the Roman Catholic tradition use the Old and New Testaments as well as the intertestamental texts, also known as the deuterocanonical texts or Apocrypha.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: Some sacred scriptures in the Bible are revealed directly from God such as the 10 Commandments in Exodus.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE
Region: Global

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: There are a number of theological positions regarding the divine inspiration of the Old and New Testaments. They all believe God was active in the composition of the texts but there is variation between the positions regarding human agency.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE
Region: Global

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE
Region: Global

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE
Region: Global

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE
Region: Global

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: Pentecostalism and the Charismatic Renewal Movement has a history of using icons such as banners as part of their liturgy. Banners are often hung inside the sanctuary of the church and are emblazoned with particular Bible verses. These banners are representations of the banners of Israel referenced throughout the Old Testament.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- At home
- Only religious public space
- Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Many banners and other icons have a picture of a dove on them. The dove is a representation of the Holy Spirit in the New Testament.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Notes: Some banners have an image of fire on them as a representation of the Acts 2 narrative where the Apostles spoke in tongues and fire rested above their heads as they spoke.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: Banners typically have a Bible verse upon them and are often presented in colors that reflect royalty.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Since the Charismatic Renewal Movement was amongst a broad swath of denominations, there are different theological positions held regarding the anthropology of a person. Some hold to a theology that a person is composed of mind, body, and spirit. Others contend that there is just body and spirit. A popular systematic theology textbook, *Renewal Theology: Systematic Theology from a Charismatic Perspective* by J. Rodman Williams contends that the Bible has distinct roles for a person's spirit and soul and thus a human is made up of body, soul, and spirit. Regardless of the differences between denominations, there is the belief that a person is more than just their corporeal body and that some part of them lives on after physical death.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

Reference: Duffield, Guy P., and Nathaniel M. Van Cleave. *Foundations of Pentecostal Theology*. Creation House, 2008. https://books.google.com/books/about/Foundations_of_Pentecostal_Theology.html?hl=&id=_EPTPAAACAAJ.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Much like other aspects of theology amongst Charismatic Renewalists, their particular theology on the human spirit and soul rests on the specific denomination they identify with. Regardless of the theological particulars and differences between denominations, the common thread between them is that there are non-physical aspects of a person's anthropology. In addition, the non-physical spirit and/or soul of a person lives beyond the physical body. When a person dies, their spirit and/or soul is separated from the body but is reunited with the body during the resurrection at the end of time.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– No

– Yes

Notes: Pentecostalism believes in an afterlife for all people but only those who have accepted God's gift of salvation through Jesus Christ will spend eternity in God's presence. The afterlife and soteriology are connected in Pentecostal theology. There is the belief that all people are sinners based on the fall of humanity described in Genesis 3. Through Jesus Christ's death on the cross and his resurrection, those who profess that Jesus Christ is their Lord and savior and are to spend eternity with God after they die. Pentecostal traditions believe that those who are saved are ushered into the presence of Jesus Christ in Heaven after they die. Those who are not saved are believed to go to Hell. There is a spectrum of belief amongst Charismatic Renewalists since they continue to adhere to their mainline or non-denominational theology regarding the afterlife. Although some Charismatic Renewalists agree with the Pentecostal position, others may not. The afterlife in Pentecostal theology is also connected with eschatology. After Jesus Christ returns to earth and wipes out evil forever, there will be a resurrection of all the dead where the spirit and body of all people will be reunited. Those who are saved receive a glorified body and spend eternity with God. Those who are not saved are sent to the Lake of Fire for eternity. See Pat Robertson answer questions about Heaven, Hell, and the Bible - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h-kdG-2ouu4>

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

Reference: Duffield, Guy P., and Nathaniel M. Van Cleave. *Foundations of Pentecostal Theology*. Creation House, 2008. https://books.google.com/books/about/Foundations_of_Pentecostal_Theology.html?hl=&id=_EPTPAAACAAJ.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatic Renewalist views about the afterlife are dependent upon the mainline

denomination they belong to. However, despite theological differences about eschatology and soteriology, there is a common thread that some people will live with God for eternity, and others will spend eternity apart from God. For an overview of the developments in Pentecostal eschatology, click this link to hear Dr. Peter Althouse share how Pentecostal eschatology has evolved: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1MhFQdlihg>

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Like other aspects of eschatology and soteriology, Charismatic Renewalists do not have a unified theology on the afterlife since adherents continue to identify with a specific denomination. Many adherents describe two spaces in the afterlife: Heaven and Hell. However, some theologies are more nuanced and believe that the spaces called a New Heaven and New Earth for those who follow God. Those who reject God spend eternity in the Lake of Fire.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Christians do not believe in reincarnation. Many traditions and denominations believe in a resurrection where a person's physical body is resurrected back to life. Some traditions believe in annihilationism where those who do not follow Jesus are annihilated and cease to exist.

Reference: Livingston, James C.. *Anatomy of the Sacred*. Prentice Hall, 2008.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Anatomy_of_the_Sacred.html?hl=&id=5pCNHwAACAAJ.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Funerals and memorial services are important rituals for Protestant and Roman Catholic traditions. The liturgy of the funeral or memorial service differs amongst denominations and traditions that identify as part of the Charismatic Renewal. Despite the differences, each denomination and tradition has some formal ritual for honoring the deceased.

Reference: Livingston, James C.. Anatomy of the Sacred. Prentice Hall, 2008.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Anatomy_of_the_Sacred.html?hl=&id=5pCNHwAACAAJ.

As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatic Renewal traditions of funerals and burials are rooted in the specific denomination of the deceased. However, some Charismatics take elements from Pentecostal funerals and burials such as attendees of the funeral wearing white instead of black to symbolize the resurrection of Jesus Christ. See - <https://www.funeralwise.com/customs/pentecostal/>

Reference: Livingston, James C.. Anatomy of the Sacred. Prentice Hall, 2008.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Anatomy_of_the_Sacred.html?hl=&id=5pCNHwAACAAJ.

Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatic Renewalists believe in supernatural beings, both good and evil. There is a belief in God, angels, cherubim, and seraphim as well as evil supernatural beings identified as Satan and demons. The way that people interact with these supernatural beings differs amongst Charismatic Renewalists due to the different denominational theologies regarding these beings. Pentecostals and Charismatics both emphasize that followers of Jesus engage the supernatural through the Baptism of the Holy Spirit. In addition, they are able to engage in spiritual warfare with evil spirits. Those who are baptized in the Holy Spirit can heal people with physical and spiritual ailments. They can also set people free who experience demonic possession or oppression. Gerald Derstine, a Mennonite Charismatic, shared a vivid description of people interacting with supernatural entities and entering into supernatural spaces: "By that time the other young people who had been lying on the floor, 'speaking in tongues' and trembling, became still and one by one they began to speak. Some of them sang. Others described heavenly scenes complete with elaborate descriptor gestures. Yet they all still lay on the floor, eyes closed, in a trance. There were prophecies of impending world events... There were words of exhortation and passages of Scripture. As each one ended his message almost invariably he would say, 'This is my body you see, this is my voice you hear, but this is from the Lord.' One word at a time."

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

Reference: Livingston, James C.. *Anatomy of the Sacred*. Prentice Hall, 2008.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Anatomy_of_the_Sacred.html?hl=&id=5pCNHwAACAAJ.

Reference: Derstine, Gerald. *Following the Fire*. Bridge-Logos Publishers, 1980.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics are monotheistic and trinitarian meaning they believe in one God that is three coeternal and consubstantial persons: The Father, Son, and Holy Spirit.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: God is often referred to in anthropomorphic terms. Common anthropomorphic terms that are used are "hand of God" or "Under the feet of Jesus." In addition, Jesus Christ is both fully God and fully man and thus exhibits anthropomorphic attributes being a human. See Rev. Derek Prince preach on "Put All Things Under the Feet of Jesus" - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yJ9Z6WBvMyc>

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics believe that God is good even in the midst of pain and suffering. Gloria Copeland is a Charismatic who writes about the goodness of God in *Charisma Magazine* - <https://www.charismamag.com/site-archives/408-columns/by-the-book/2055-god-is-good>

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

Reference: Copeland, Gloria. "God Is Good". *Charisma Magazine*, October 31, 2006.
<https://charismamag.com/spiritled-living/purposeidentity/god-is-good/>.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Trinitarian - Father, Son, and Holy Spirit

Notes: Charismatic Renewalists believe in Trinitarian Monotheism. They believe in a monotheistic God who consists of the Father, Jesus Christ, and the Holy Spirit. Each person of the Trinity is distinct from one another but also fully God. There are some differences in the theology of the Trinity between Charismatic Renewalists within mainline denominations but they all believe in Trinitarian Monotheism. There are some Pentecostals who identify as "Oneness Pentecostals." Dr. David A. Reed explains, "There is a sense in which God is a 'trinity,' but it is reserved for the threefold way that God reveals Himself and acts in the world. That is, God is radically one in His transcendence, but threefold in His immanence. However different they are in function, these three "manifestations" converge ultimately in Jesus Christ, the One in whom 'dwells all the fullness of the Godhead bodily' (Col. 2:9), which is why the oneness of God and His name are so vigorously defended."

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

Reference: Synan, Vinson. *The Holiness-pentecostal Tradition*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing, 1997. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=Q-npoRWoZuUC>.

Reference: Synan, Vinson, and David Reed. "The "finished Work" Pentecostal Churches". In *The Century of the Holy Spirit*. Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson, 2001.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

Reference: Synan, Vinson. *The Holiness-pentecostal Tradition*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing, 1997. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=Q-npoRWoZuUC>.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics believe that God has knowledge of the United States and they believe God wants his followers to expand their influence throughout the nation. Civic leaders have a responsibility to God since God knows what is best for the nation. See Pat Robertson's presidential bid announcement in 1988.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WKahKMnbMJE>

Reference: Neuhaus, Richard John. *The Naked Public Square*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing, 1986. https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=U_EIkFKLNACc.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: God knows about the entire world since he is the creator of the world and everything in it. His knowledge is not limited to one particular section of the globe.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: God knows the hearts and desires of people. Charismatic and Pentecostal preachers often exhort their congregants to get their hearts right before God. See this sermon about the importance of the heart from Joel Osteen - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-bW2ZTV33Jk>

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Theological positions on God's foreknowledge vary based upon the denomination of a group. Some Charismatic Renewalists hold to a Calvinist position where God knows what people will choose to do or not do, particularly in regards to salvation. Other Charismatics hold an Arminian position where God gives people free will to choose, particularly when it comes to salvation.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The connection between God and rewards is paramount to some Charismatic and Pentecostal adherents. Teachings such as the Prosperity Gospel are rooted in Pentecostal and Charismatic teachings that there is a direct cause and effect in regards to a believers' faith. If a believer has enough faith that God can bless them and can also demonstrate that faith in a tangible way such as giving an extra tithe, then God will bless that person financially, physically, emotionally, or in whatever other way the believer seeks.

Reference: Bowler, Kate. *Blessed*. Oxford University Press, 2018.

<https://books.google.com/books/about/Blessed.html?hl=&id=oJc4DwAAQBAJ>.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics and Pentecostals believe that believers can and ought to hear directly from God. God speaks through reading the Bible, prayer, dreams, words of knowledge, and prophetic utterances. Charismatic preachers exhort their congregations to hear from God and seek his voice. Here is a message from Pastor Robert Morris on how to hear God's voice - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lscKxdYtq9g>

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics believe that God speaks through dreams. Practitioners are encouraged to seek out counsel regarding their dreams and find prophetic insight into what God is speaking to them. See Christ for the Nations training video on how to understand prophetic dreams - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=frDCYwW10AE>

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Notes: Divination is considered an evil practice amongst Charismatic Christians. This is consistent among Charismatics in mainline and evangelical traditions.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Pentecostalism and Charismatics believe that all adherents who are baptized in the Holy Spirit can speak to God and speak God's prophetic words to others.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Prophecy through those who practice the spiritual gift of prophecy

Notes: God speaks to people through speaking in tongues and the gift of prophecy. All Charismatics are encouraged to prophesy and speak God's words that they receive. See Bill Johnson's teaching on the gift of prophecy - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T-uwdMuyzUA>

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics believe that God is watching how people live their lives. Preachers regularly exhort their congregations to be mindful of how they live and to live according to the precepts prescribed in the Bible. See John Osteen's sermon <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7dJADbZ4iHI>

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Pentecostals and Charismatic Renewalists point to the Ten Commandments and the teachings of Jesus Christ in the Gospel accounts to show that God is against murder.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics believe that God created sex for pleasure and pro-creation within monogamous marriage. Charismatic pastors regularly teach on sex and lust. See Pastor Robert Morris teach on Sex and Lust - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h2tKvFBh234>

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatic Renewalists teach against adultery. They point to the 10 Commandments and the teachings of Jesus to support their position that God does not condone adultery.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatic Renewalists teach against incest. They contend that God is against incest based on numerous Biblical texts condemning incest, particularly in the Pentateuch.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: homosexual practices

Notes: There is debate amongst some Charismatic traditions regarding LGBTQ issues. Charismatics in mainline denominations may be more liberal in their theology and practice. More conservative Charismatics believe that God condemns homosexual practices. See Dr. Michael Brown's teaching on homosexuality and the church - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4dknQrMQxy4>

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics believe that God is against sorcery and witchcraft. See Pat Robertson address witchcraft here - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LAKIE1_FiQA

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatic preachers often teach against gossip. They contend that God desires for people to live in peace with one another and gossip is a disruptor of that end. See Joel Osteen teach on Keeping the Peace - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sNVF7QDVYCY>

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatic Protestants believe that there are two ordinances of the church: Baptism and Communion. Roman Catholic Charismatics adhere to the Roman Catholic ordinances beyond what is prescribed by Protestant traditions.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics believe that God desires for all people to be saved. Followers of Jesus are commanded to make disciples and share the gospel with others. Charismatic organizations such as Youth With A Mission and Christ for the Nations train practitioners to evangelize through the power of the Holy Spirit.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

Region: Global

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatic teachings on living with God for eternity in the afterlife vary amongst the different mainline and evangelical denominations. However, they all teach that there will be joy for eternity. See Benny Hinn's teaching on life in Heaven - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a3nJHy7fOjw>

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Charismatic renewalists believe in bodily resurrection. The believer maintains their identity after death but is resurrected in a new body. A resurrected believer lives in the New Heaven and New Earth with Jesus Christ.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Many Charismatics do not adhere to a reward system but others do. There are Charismatics who adhere to Pentecostal Prosperity Gospel doctrines that teach God wants to bless people financially and physically in this life. Traditional Charismatics from mainline denominations maintain positions on prosperity that are in line with their denomination.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Amongst some Charismatics there is a belief that God will allow social disruption and unrest in the United States as a result of America's unfaithfulness to their Christian heritage. See an interview between Phil Robertson and Pat Robertson regarding how America is being destroyed by the Devil - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4_9pQ1DO--U
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Messianic beliefs are a crucial aspect of Charismatic Renewal theology. The term messiah means "anointed one" in Hebrew and is translated as "Christ" in Greek. Jesus Christ can be translated as Jesus Messiah or Jesus the anointed one. Jesus Christ is the central figure of Christianity and his life, death, and resurrection are connected to most theological doctrines and beliefs within Protestant, Roman Catholic, and Orthodox traditions. Pentecostal and Charismatic Renewalists emphasize the person and work of Jesus Christ in their theology and practice. Although there may be some variations theologically between sub-traditions and denominations within Pentecostal and Charismatic traditions, there is an emphasis on Jesus' atonement for the sins of the world through his death and his power over death and evil through his resurrection from the dead. Theological differences abound within Christianity regarding the effects of the atonement of Jesus Christ. Pentecostal and Charismatic Renewalists believe that physical healing is part of the atonement. Followers of Jesus who are Baptized in the Holy Spirit have the power to physically heal people just as Jesus did in the gospel accounts in the New Testament.

Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatic Renewalists believe that Jesus Christ will return to do battle with Satan and remove evil from the world so that the New Heaven and New Earth will be brought forth. All pain, suffering, loss, and death will cease when Jesus Christ returns. Those who accepted God's gift of salvation through Jesus Christ will live in the New Heaven and New Earth with God forever.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

Reference: Duffield, Guy P., and Nathaniel M. Van Cleave. *Foundations of Pentecostal Theology*. Creation House, 2008.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Foundations_of_Pentecostal_Theology.html?hl=&id=_EPTPAAACAAJ.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global

Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: Many Pentecostal traditions believe that Jesus Christ is the king of the Kingdom of God and his second-coming return will fully usher in his rule and reign on earth. Some Pentecostal denominations, such as The Foursquare Church, weave the concept of King Jesus into their branding. See <https://www.foursquare.org/about/beliefs/> Charismatic Renewalists may or may not hold to the traditional Pentecostal view of

Jesus Christ's rule and reign on earth. Positions regarding the messiah as a political figure is dependent on the specific theology of the particular mainline or evangelical denomination that a practitioner adheres to.

Reference: Duffield, Guy P., and Nathaniel M. Van Cleave. *Foundations of Pentecostal Theology*. Creation House, 2008.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Foundations_of_Pentecostal_Theology.html?hl=&id=_EPTPAAACAAJ.

Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: Hebrews 4:14-16 says, "Since, then, we have a great high priest who has passed through the heavens, Jesus, the Son of God, let us hold fast to our confession. For we do not have a high priest who is unable to sympathize with our weaknesses, but we have one who in every respect has been tested as we are, yet without sin. Let us therefore approach the throne of grace with boldness, so that we may receive mercy and find grace to help in time of need." This verse undergirds Pentecostal and Charismatic Renewalist belief that Jesus Christ is the supreme high priest who offers atonement for sin.

Reference: Duffield, Guy P., and Nathaniel M. Van Cleave. *Foundations of Pentecostal Theology*. Creation House, 2008.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Foundations_of_Pentecostal_Theology.html?hl=&id=_EPTPAAACAAJ.

Other purpose:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Eschatology is an important theological concept in Charismatic traditions although there is a spectrum of belief amongst Charismatics due to denominational affiliations. Many Charismatics believe that Jesus Christ ushered in the Kingdom of God through his life, ministry, death, and resurrection. The Kingdom of God is believed to be in process and will fully culminate at the end of time. There is much speculation amongst Charismatics about how and when Jesus Christ will return and the specific nuances surrounding his return.

Reference: Ladd, George Eldon, and Donald Alfred Hagner. *A Theology of the New Testament*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing, 1993. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=eldkM00EdIAC>.

Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Some Charismatics believe that they are living in the eschaton due to their interpretation of their Kingdom of God theology. Time is on a trajectory to the end and there is a belief that every day is the end times. See Pat Robertson's teaching on the end times - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6hFOFLNS7oo>

Reference: Duffield, Guy P., and Nathaniel M. Van Cleave. *Foundations of Pentecostal Theology*. Creation House, 2008.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Foundations_of_Pentecostal_Theology.html?hl=&id=_EPTPAAACAAJ.

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

Notes: Although some Charismatics try to determine a date for when Jesus Christ returns, many Charismatics believe that no one knows when Jesus Christ will return.

Reference: Boyer, Paul. *When Time Shall Be No More*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1992.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: Some Charismatics believe that Jesus Christ's return is happening within their lifetime. They interpret the wars, famines, and civil unrest in the United States and the world as evidence of Jesus Christ's second coming.

Reference: Boyer, Paul. *When Time Shall Be No More*. Harvard University Press, 2009.
https://books.google.com/books/about/When_Time_Shall_Be_No_More.html?hl=&id=FyTeW7vQ8K4C.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Reference: Boyer, Paul. *When Time Shall Be No More*. Harvard University Press, 2009.
https://books.google.com/books/about/When_Time_Shall_Be_No_More.html?hl=&id=FyTeW7vQ8K4C.

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics believe that God will judge all inhabitants of the world throughout time. Those who have accepted Jesus Christ as their savior will spend eternity with God and those who rejected Christ will spend eternity apart from God.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

Notes: There is debate amongst different mainline Protestant traditions regarding what the restoration will look like. However, many Charismatics believe that God will create a New Heaven and New Earth that restores the essence of what was lost in the Garden of Eden. See the Bible Project video on Heaven and Earth - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Zy2AQIK6C5k>

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: There are different positions regarding the eschaton, particularly regarding interpretations of the rapture. Some evangelical Charismatics believe in dispensationalism and articulate beliefs in a literal tribulation and rapture. Some people will survive the tribulation.

Reference: Boyer, Paul. *When Time Shall Be No More*. Harvard University Press, 2009.
https://books.google.com/books/about/When_Time_Shall_Be_No_More.html?hl=&id=FyTeW7vQ8K4C.

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Many Charismatics believe in a literal rapture where Jesus Christ rescues all living Christians from Earth before God's judgment begins.

Reference: Boyer, Paul. *When Time Shall Be No More*. Harvard University Press, 2009.

https://books.google.com/books/about/When_Time_Shall_Be_No_More.html?hl=&id=FyTeW7vQ8K4C.

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:
– No

↳ Other survival condition:
– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Reference: Duffield, Guy P., and Nathaniel M. Van Cleave. *Foundations of Pentecostal Theology*. Creation House, 2008. https://books.google.com/books/about/Foundations_of_Pentecostal_Theology.html?hl=&id=_EPTPAAACAAJ.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatic Renewalists and Pentecostals continued to adhere to American conservative social norms within their churches during the Second Wave Renewal. However, the Jesus Movement that began in California in the late 1960s challenged the notion of blending conventional and moral distinctions. The Jesus Movement consisted primarily of hippies from the counter-cultural movement. Although they were theologically in line with many Pentecostal and Evangelical traditions of the time, they promoted a more casual and accepting atmosphere in their gatherings that offended leaders and practitioners from other denominations. The Jesus Movement changed the style of worship music by blending secular folk and rock with Christian lyrics. The casual and contemporary feel of the Jesus Movement resonated with baby boomers who were coming of age during the late 1960s and early 1970s. Today, there are Protestant leaders who condemn what the Jesus Movement and their contemporaries did to Protestant Christianity in regards to both the embrace of Charismatic elements as well as the casual embrace of the contemporary counter-cultural movement within the church. See John MacArthur's views on Calvary Chapel and the Jesus Movement - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8YH7TZkn45M>

Reference: Eskridge, Larry. *God's Forever Family*. USA: Oxford University Press, 2013. https://books.google.com/books/about/God_s_Forever_Family.html?hl=&id=kw2qKgZrte4C.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:
– Present and clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: Moral teachings within Charismatic traditions are rooted in the teachings of Jesus Christ in the New Testament. Hermeneutics regarding morality based upon the Old Testament and other parts of the New Testament are woven through the person and work of Jesus Christ.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: Moral norms are taught by Jesus Christ in various parables and narratives in the Gospel accounts. In addition, much of the theology embraced by Charismatic Renewalists see other aspects of morality given from God the Father in the Old Testament as well as through teachings from apostles like Paul and Peter.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: Honesty and trustworthiness have taken a hit within Charismatic and Pentecostal traditions over the years due to skepticism of prosperity teachings and criminal financial activity amongst some pastors such as Jim Bakker in the late 1980s.

Reference: Synan, Vinson. *The Century of the Holy Spirit*. Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson, 2000.

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

Notes: A popular verse from the Bible used to encourage adherents to be courageous is Deuteronomy 31:6, "Be strong and courageous. Do not be afraid or terrified because of them, for the LORD your God goes with you."

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: Popular Bible verses that encourage adherents being compassionate are Exodus 34:6, "Then the Lord passed by in front of him and proclaimed, "The Lord, the Lord God, compassionate and gracious, slow to anger, and abounding in lovingkindness and truth" and Matthew 14:14, "And when Jesus went out He saw a great multitude, and He was moved with compassion for them, and healed their sick." One example of Charismatic benevolence ministry is YWAM. Youth With A Mission (YWAM) began in 1960 as an evangelistic-charismatic agency focused on training youth to evangelize throughout the world. One of the primary ministries of YWAM is mercy ships to provide medical care to people all over the world. The first ship, M.V. Anastasis, was commissioned in 1977 for medical care. The mercy ship ministry continues today - <https://ywamships.org/>

Reference: Synan, Vinson. *The Century of the Holy Spirit*. Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson, 2000.

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

Notes: Forgiveness and mercy are important virtues within Charismatic Renewal traditions. They are based on the concepts of God's forgiveness of sins through the death and resurrection of Jesus Christ.

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Notes: Many Charismatics believe in moderation in regards to substances like alcohol. There is also moderation as it relates to media content such as music and movies.

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Notes: The virtue of hope is rooted in Bible verses such as 1 Peter 1:3 that says, "Blessed be the God and Father of our Lord Jesus Christ, who according to His great mercy has caused us to be born again to a living hope through the resurrection of Jesus Christ from the dead." Charismatics are encouraged to be hopeful because they have hope in the resurrection of Jesus Christ.

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatic preachers often encourage their congregations to be thankful, even in the midst of hardships and challenges. See Pastor Robert Morris teach on Gratitude - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mQvKQ6Dz36I>

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Notes: Faith is a foundational virtue within Charismatic Renewal traditions. All followers of Jesus Christ are expected to demonstrate faith when they accept Jesus Christ as their Lord and Savior. There is also a distinct spiritual gift of faith that not all believers are granted. This gift allows the believer to manifest faith in ways that others are not able to.

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Notes: Wisdom is highly revered in Charismatic Renewal traditions. Wisdom is a spiritual gift that is identified in 1 Corinthians 12. The gift of wisdom allows a person to speak into a person's life or into a particular circumstance with great insight and righteousness.

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Notes: Discernment is a spiritual gift listed in 1 Corinthians 12. The spiritual gift of discernment allows believers to discern good and evil in the physical and spiritual realm. Charismatic Renewalists believe that those who are baptized in the Holy Spirit must practice discernment and use it to evaluate what is going on in their lives and the world around them.

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics believe that sex should be practiced between a married couple of one man and one woman. Abstinence should be practiced by those who are single.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Many Charismatics believe that those who identify as LGBTQ are sinning against the

original design of marriage and of sex. They base their position on teachings in the Old and New Testaments.

Reference: Brown, Michael L.. *Can You Be Gay and Christian?*. Charisma Media, 2014.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Can_You_Be_Gay_and_Christian.html?hl=&id=Jpw9AwAAQBAJ.

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Many Charismatics believe that those who identify as LGBTQ are sinning against the original design of marriage and of sex. They base their position on teachings in the Old and New Testaments.

Reference: Brown, Michael L.. *Can You Be Gay and Christian?*. Charisma Media, 2014.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Can_You_Be_Gay_and_Christian.html?hl=&id=Jpw9AwAAQBAJ.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Fasting is not required but it is a common practice for many practioners within Charismatic traditions. Fasting is practiced when a practitioner wants to seek God at a deeper level. See Pastor Derek Prince's teaching on fasting and praying - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h6jvnfdUQhl>

Reference: Wallis, Arthur. *God's Chosen Fast*. CLC Publications, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=KpqhZtcVvpQC>.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular

Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics believe that going to church services and prayer meetings ought to be a regular part of a persons' life. Although church attendance is not usually required it is often unofficially mandetory.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Most Protestant denominations undergird all ethical precepts under Jesus Christ's teaching on the two greatest commandments: Love God and love your neighbor as yourself. The Ten Commandments and all other ethical precepts fall within these two commandments from Jesus. Click to view a sermon on these teachings from Pastor Matt Chandler - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IUBhQv4M0To>

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:
I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– I don't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Catholic Church has a long history of poverty relief efforts in the United States and throughout the world. In 2020, Pope Francis called upon Catholic Charismatic groups to provide support and assistance to those in need due to the Coronavirus pandemic.

Reference: [licas.news](https://www.licas.news/2020/06/01/pope-francis-calls-on-catholic-charismatic-groups-to-work-for-justice/) reporter. “Pope Francis Calls on Catholic Charismatic Groups to Work for Justice”. [licas.news](https://www.licas.news/2020/06/01/pope-francis-calls-on-catholic-charismatic-groups-to-work-for-justice/), June 1, 2020. <https://www.licas.news/2020/06/01/pope-francis-calls-on-catholic-charismatic-groups-to-work-for-justice/>.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: There are numerous Pentecostal and Charismatic schools throughout the United States. There are also colleges and universities that hold to Charismatic doctrines and have degree programs for aspiring Charismatic clergy.

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics are able to attend public or private schools of their choosing.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: It depends on the denomination of the charismatic church. Some denominations are highly bureaucratic whereas others are not.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatic churches must engage with other bureaucracies such as local, state, and federal

government agencies in order to do business.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics in the United States are provided water through local municipal agencies.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Tithing is a common practice in Christianity and it is particularly important to Pentecostal and some Charismatic groups. As many mainline denominations embraced Pentecostal practices and theology during the 1960s, the ground was tilled for the rise of the "Word of Faith" movement, also known as the "Health and Wealth Gospel" or "Prosperity Gospel." The Word of Faith movement teaches that God wants to bless people financially and materially. In order to receive God's blessings, people need to demonstrate their faith through verbal declarations and through sacrificial financial giving such as tithing. There are some denominations and Charismatic adherents who disagree with Prosperity Gospel teachings.

Reference: Bowler, Kate. *Blessed*. Oxford University Press, 2018.

<https://books.google.com/books/about/Blessed.html?hl=&id=oJc4DwAAQBAJ>.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents pay local, state, and federal taxes if they earn an income. Churches are not subject to taxation if they are a registered 501c3 non-profit organization under the IRS.

Reference: IRS. "Exemption Requirements - 501c3 Organizations". Internal Revenue Service, n.d.. <https://www.irs.gov/charities-non-profits/charitable-organizations/exemption-requirements-501c3-organizations>.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatic Christians in the United States are able to engage with local law enforcement.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatic Christians in the United States have access to the judicial system.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: It depends on whether the state permits the death penalty. Many Christians, including Charismatic Christians, are opposed to the death penalty.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1960 CE - 1980 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics adhere to the United States Constitution, state constitutions, and other local laws. There is debate amongst Charismatics about the limits of obeying and adhering to laws that violate religious convictions. Debates surrounding abortion and LGBTQ rights are common amongst Charismatics.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics are allowed to serve in the military and many of them choose to volunteer for military service. In addition, there are Charismatic chaplains in the United States military.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Bibliography

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Bennett, Dennis. *Nine O'clock in the Morning*. Alachua, FL: Bridge Logos, 1970.

Reference: Yes, Boyer, Paul. *When Time Shall Be No More*. Harvard University Press, 2009.
https://books.google.com/books/about/When_Time_Shall_Be_No_More.html?hl=&id=FyTeW7vQ8K4C...

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<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=KpqhZtcVvpQC>.

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<https://www.irs.gov/charities-non-profits/charitable-organizations/exemption-requirements-501c3-organizations>.